

BIOMORPHOLOGY, SYSTEMATICS AND ALLERGENIC PROPERTIES OF PINUS L. SPECIES

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Abstract: In this article, the biomorphology, growth areas, systematic analysis and allergenic properties of *Pinus strobus*, *Pinus pallasiana*, *Pinus silvestris* from the species of the *Pinus L.* series, common in Andijan city, were described based on various literature.

Key words: area, allergen, phenology, pantoporate, pollen, taxon

Pinus L. (Pinaceae), with over 100 widely recognized species, is the largest extant genus of conifers. Pines are ecologically important as a major, often dominant component of boreal, sub-alpine, temperate, and tropical forests, as well as arid woodlands. Economically, pines are an important source of wood, paper, resins, charcoal, food (particularly seeds), and ornamentals [1]. Pines are ecologically important as a major, often dominant component of boreal, sub-alpine, temperate, and tropical forests, as well as arid woodlands. Economically, pines are an important source of wood, paper, resins, charcoal, food and ornamentals [2].

Systematics of conifers: Section. Pine family (Pynophyta or Gymnospermae) Family. Pines (Pinaceae Lindl.) Category. Pine, pine (*Pinus L.*)

PINUS L. is a large, perennial, evergreen plant. Branches grow spirally and thus the plant gives the appearance of a conical or pyramidal structure. Sporophytic plant body is differentiated into roots, stem and acicular (needle-like) leaves. A tap root with few root hair is present but it disappears soon. Later on many lateral roots develop, which help in absorption and fixation. The ultimate branches of these roots

are covered by a covering of fungal hyphae called ectotrophic mycorrhiza. The stem is cylindrical and erect, and remains covered with bark. Branching is monopodial. Two types of branches are present: long shoots and dwarf shoots. These are also known as branches of unlimited and limited growth, respectively. Long shoots contain apical bud and grow indefinitely. Many scaly leaves are present on the long shoot. Dwarf shoots are devoid of any apical bud and thus are limited in their growth. They arise on the long shoot in the axil of scaly leaves. A dwarf shoot has two scaly leaves called prophylls, followed by 5-13 cataphylls arranged in 2/5 phyllotaxy, and 1-5 needles. The leaves are of two types, i.e., foliage and scaly. Scaly leaves are thin, brown-coloured and scale like and develop only on long as well as dwarf shoots. Foliage leaves are present at the apex of the dwarf shoots only. Foliage leaves are large, needle-like, and vary in number from 1 to 5 in different species [3].

The book of the flora of Uzbekistan lists mainly 4 species, of which currently *Pinus montana* Mill. the species is called *Pinus silvestris* L. [4,5].

***Pinus strobus* L.** Veymutov pine is a large tree with a height of 35-50 m and a diameter of 1.5 m, with wide and pyramidal branches. The shell of the body is cracked, dark gray in color. Branches are thin, brown-gray, sparsely hairy. The jacket is covered with glue beads. The leaves are three-sided, 5-10 cm long, soft, thin, blue in color, and are kept on the tree for 2-3 years. (Figure 1)

General view of *Pinus strobus* L.

Pinus Pallasiana Lamb. Crimean or Pallas pine is a large tree with a height of 35 m and a diameter of up to 50 cm. The bark of its body is dark gray, and its branches are reddish in color. The buds are conical, with a sharp tip, covered with resin. The leaves are dark green, hard, shiny, with a sharp tip, 15-16 cm long, twice as long as those of the common pine. They are placed in groups of 2 on a branch. The dome is very large. Pollinated in May. The dome is made in the spring of the third year after pollination and fertilization. Ripe dome is yellow-brown, 5-10 cm tall, larger than that of a common pine. The seed is also large, 6 mm long, winged.

Pinus silvestris L. An ordinary pine is a tree with a height of 30-40 m and a diameter of 1 m. Lives up to 600 years in favorable conditions. The bark of the body is thick and vertically split, the underside is brown, and the face is orange or reddish in color. A thin bark separates from the trunk and branches. The tree forms sparse branches in the form of a circle. In pine groves, 115 lower branches dry up and fall off. The branches of an adult pine are egg-shaped [5]. (Figure 2).

A view of the dome of Pinus Pallasiana. General view of Pinus silvestris L.

Distribution and Ecology. Vietnam, Cambodia, Philippines, Malaysia and Indonesia. In Malesia, found in N & C Sumatra, and in the Philippines, on Mindoro I. and Zambales prov., Luzon I. In Vietnam found in large stands or in small groups at Lai Chau, Son La, Lang Son, Bac Thai, Ha Bac, Quang Ninh, Thanh Hoa, Nghe An, Ha Tinh, Quang Binh and Thua Thien Hue provinces, but mainly in Kon Tum and Lam Dong provinces. It has the most southerly distribution of any pine and is the only pine occurring south of the Equator, to 2.10° S in the Barisian Range of

Sumatra. It is found at elevations of (0)800-2000 m, usually in open, savannah-like areas that are frequently burned by native peoples, but also in tropical broadleaf forest. The best-developed forests are to be found around Lake Toba in northern Sumatra [6].

In areas of frequent fire, seedlings of this species may develop a "grass stage." See the "Remarks" section HERE for details on "grass stage" growth. This is a light-demanding, heat- and drought-tolerant tree, growing well on sandy and red soils. In north Vietnam, this species is one of the principal tree species planted on bare or bushy hills, having the function of protecting against erosion and land-deformation. Young trees are slow-growing during the first five years, later rather fast-growing. From 15 years onward, the resin can be harvested. Natural regeneration is good, especially on open lands. Flowers in May-June; cones mature in October-November of the following year (FIPI 1996). USDA hardiness zone. Zone 10 (cold hardiness limit between -1°C and +4.4°C) [7].

Medicinal properties. Buds, essential oil and resin extracted from the body are used in medicine. Buds and leafy branches contain essential oil, C, K, and E, carotene, anthocyanins, bitter, astringent and other substances. Essential oil mainly consists of pinene, limonene, bornylacetate, terpenoids and other substances. Plant bud tincture is used as an expectorant, disinfectant and diuretic, essential oil is used for inhalation in case of upper respiratory tract infections. used for A solution of essential oil in alcohol is sprayed to improve the smell of rooms (mostly hospitals). Pine resin produces turpentine, rosin, and pistachio coal. Turpentine is used in various ointments, balms, and other mixtures to treat neuralgia, colds, and other colds. It is inhaled when the respiratory tract is infected. It is sprayed into the rooms and is used in the treatment of scabies, eczema and ringworm as part of Vishnevsky ointment. Rosin is included in various ointments. Pistachio drug-carbolene tablet is used when the stomach is at rest.

Pine resin is used to treat many inflammations, colds and infectious diseases. Indications for its use include: - inflammatory diseases of the gums and mucous membranes of the mouth; - flu, SARS, sore throat; - toothache caused by caries; -

varicose veins in the legs expansion;-skin damage-scratches and cuts, used for purulent wounds Joint diseases:-rheumatism, radiculitis, arthrosis;-juice has an additional healing effect during the recovery period;muscle pain-bruises and bruises;Diseases of the digestive system:-gastritis and heartburn;-dermatitis and other inflammatory skin diseases. In addition, in the book of the famous doctor Ibn Sina about medicinal plants: the leaves of this tree are tied against hot swellings; hinders [8].

Allergic levels. Overview. While pine tree allergy is relatively uncommon, there are two main allergens of concern that come from pine trees: pine nuts and pine pollen. Pine nuts are the edible seeds of certain species of pine trees, and are used in a variety of foods, including Italian pesto. Research into the health benefits of pine pollen is ongoing. The results so far suggest it has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. These qualities could be beneficial in treating a variety of health conditions, although more research is needed. People with a pollen allergy should avoid using pine pollen.

When people think of allergies, they often think of pollen from flowers or grasses. While pine trees are beautiful to look at, they release pollen that can trigger allergies in some people. When these three allergens are released into the air, they can cause reactions like itchy eyes, sneezing, and coughing. This happens mostly during spring and early summer when tree pollen levels are higher. If you experience severe reactions, it may be beneficial to consult an Allergy Doctor in San Antonio for personalized treatment and advice. Let’s take a closer look at how pine trees might affect individuals and how to manage any potential symptoms.

Common Signs of Pine Tree Allergies. People who are allergic to pine trees might experience symptoms similar to other pollen allergies. Some common signs include:

- Itchy, red, or watery eyes
- Sneezing or a runny nose
- Coughing or wheezing
- Skin rash or itching (often called pine tree rash)

These symptoms can range from mild to severe, depending on the individual's immune system and the amount of pollen exposure. Some people may also experience asthma-like symptoms, especially if they are exposed to pine tree pollen for a long time. Allergic reactions occur when the body's immune system mistakenly identifies substances (like tree pollen) as harmful. Pine tree pollen is one of the most common triggers, but the sap and oils from pine needles can also cause reactions. For some individuals, even brief exposure or close contact with pine trees can lead to uncomfortable symptoms. In other cases, being near pine trees or in wooded areas for long periods can trigger allergies, especially during pollen season. Managing Pine Tree Allergies. If you suspect you have a pine tree allergy, there are steps you can take to lower your symptoms. Here are some of the most effective measures:

Use Over-the-counter Medication. Antihistamines can help control common allergy symptoms like itching, sneezing, and a runny nose. **Keep Windows Closed** Pollen can enter your home through open windows, so keep them closed during high pollen times to reduce exposure indoors.

Wash Clothing and Shower. Shower and wash your clothes after spending time outdoors to remove any pollen that might have settled on you.

Use Air Purifiers. Air purifiers with HEPA filters can help reduce indoor pollen and improve air quality. **When to See a Doctor.** If your symptoms worsen or you suspect a pine tree allergy, it's best to consult a medical professional. An allergist can perform further testing, such as skin or blood tests, to confirm the cause of your allergy. Once diagnosed, they can offer more personalized advice or suggest other treatments that may help manage symptoms more effectively.

Potential Complications. If left untreated, pine tree allergies can cause complications such as sinus infections, asthma attacks, or chronic discomfort. People with asthma should be cautious around pine trees, as the pollen can trigger breathing issues. In severe cases, immediate medical help may be necessary [9].

Species of the genus PINUS L. play an important role in the ecosystem. The plants belonging to this family, mainly pines, belong to a large and ancient category of trees and have several important ecological, economic and cultural values. At the

same time, because these species of representatives of this family have the characteristics of anemophilic pollination, they also cause allergies. Today, the biology, ecology and medicinal properties of this species are well studied in Uzbekistan, and the study of the morphology of their pollen and the study and monitoring of the levels of allergic effects are of great importance. This study was conducted on the basis of the literature, and more detailed information will be provided in our future research work.

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9. Get allergy updates straight to your inbox <https://juniperallergy.com/can-you-be-allergic-to-pine-trees>.